

METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF SERVICE IN DATA TRANSMISSION NETWORKS

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Abstract— in this work the monitoring methods for ensuring the quality of service in data transmission networks. The importance of network monitoring and analysis for network administrators, as well as the various monitoring methods, are presented.

Keywords— Monitoring, traffic, network, quality of service (QoS), packet-switching data

INTRODUCTION

The important task for various spheres of human activity, including work, shopping, business trips, mail transportation, etc., is to increase labor productivity by improving the efficiency of information exchange.

Today, experts and analysts estimate that 90% of transportation (physical) movements of people are related to information purposes, and their reduction is possible through the use of information technologies and telecommunications tools. At the current stage of development, remote work technologies and online communication allow individuals and organizations to perform many tasks without the need for physical movement of people, which can significantly reduce transportation costs and the burden on transportation systems.

In this regard, the creation of a modern national information infrastructure becomes one of the most promising and dynamically developing basic infrastructures of society, contributing to the overall progress and sustainable development of the country. Therefore, the construction of a modern national information infrastructure, based on the development of a concept and, accordingly, a state program, becomes a key element for the successful development of the country.

As early as 1993, the United States was the first in the world to introduce a state program called the "National Information Infrastructure" (NII), aimed at developing and interpenetrating information structures and uniting various networks and data transmission technologies. According to experts and analysts, telecommuting, online shopping, video conferencing, and electronic document exchange help reduce the transportation load in the U.S. by 10%-20%, which is equivalent to:

- Reducing 6 million daily commutes to work,
- 3 billion annual shopping trips,
- 13 million annual business trips,
- More than 900 million kilometers of annual mail transportation.

These estimates show that a national information infrastructure has a significant impact on various spheres of human activity, including politics, economics, science, culture, education, industry, and other fields.

In this regard, a strategic task for a developed country is the formation of a national information infrastructure. The issue of creating it must be considered from the perspective of its two main components: telecommunications and informational. The telecommunications component consists of data transmission networks with packet switching and means of transmitting various types of information (data, voice, video), which serve as the transport foundation of the information infrastructure. The informational component includes means of information search, processing, and storage, i.e., data centers and individual servers. Thus, the telecommunications component of the information infrastructure consists of packet-switched data (PD) networks based on the IP protocol. Initially, the IP protocol was designed solely for data transmission services, but as it evolved, it became applicable for real-time services (voice, video, and multimedia), which require guaranteed quality of service. The construction of PD networks with packet switching based on the IP protocol enables the provision of a full range of data, voice, and video transmission services on a unified platform.

The use of a single infrastructure of PD networks based on the IP protocol for the transmission of data, voice, graphics, and video data provides significant advantages. Therefore, the transition to an IP network as a unified environment for transmitting all types of real-time traffic requires guaranteed quality of service. However, it is important to note that within the architecture of the IP network, it is necessary to support various multimedia traffic with diverse quality of service (QoS) requirements. Different types of real-time traffic have different demands on quality of service levels.

It is clear that the further development of an internal private network is crucial, and it is essential that network administrators know how to manually manage different types of traffic passing through their network. Traffic monitoring and analysis are necessary for more effective diagnostics and solving problems when they arise, so that network services do not remain non-functional for extended periods. There are various tools that help administrators in network traffic monitoring and analysis. This dissertation focuses on monitoring methods oriented towards routers.

The Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) is an application-level protocol that is part of the TCP/IP protocol suite. It allows administrators to monitor network performance, find and solve network problems, and plan network development. It collects traffic statistics for an endpoint through passive sensors integrated with routers. There are three versions: SNMPv1, SNMPv2, and SNMPv3. SNMPv2 is based on SNMPv1 and offers a range of improvements,

such as the addition of protocol operations. SNMP has three key components: Managed Devices, Agents, and Network Management Systems (NMSs).

Remote Monitoring (RMON) includes various network monitors and console systems for modifying the data obtained from network monitoring. It is an extension of SNMP and the Management Information Base (MIB). Unlike SNMP, which must send queries to obtain information, RMON can configure triggers that "monitor" the network based on specific criteria. RMON provides administrators with the ability to manage local networks, as well as remotely from a single location. It monitors the network level. RMON has two versions: RMON and RMON2. RMON2 allows monitoring all levels of the network. It focuses on IP traffic and application-layer traffic.

NetFlow is an extension introduced in Cisco routers that provides the ability to capture IP network traffic passing through an interface. By analyzing the data provided by NetFlow, a network administrator can determine things like the source and destination of traffic, class of service, and causes of congestion. NetFlow consists of three components: FlowCaching (flow caching), FlowCollector (flow information collector), and Data Analyzer (data analyzer).

As an example, consider the network monitoring system TheDude. The global network includes three local networks, which contain at least 15 personal computers, three switches (24 ports, 1000 Mbps) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Data Transmission Network

All of these network devices are connected with optical patch cords to ensure high-speed 1000 Mbps connections. Each piece of network equipment is configured with SNMP version SNMPv2. The DUDE server services the local area network (LAN). Several servers, such as DHCP, mail server, Openfire, Asterisk, fax server, and others, are also installed and configured on a machine running the Linux Ubuntu operating system. In this experiment, we were able to monitor:

- The status of the equipment (on/off),
- The channel throughput: receive (Rx) and transmit (Tx) between all equipment,
- Trend monitoring (trend monitoring functions). All SNMP management functions allow continuous monitoring of certain attribute values of managed objects, recorded in the MIB, over a specific period of time.

Furthermore, one of the advantages of this system is the ability to remotely connect to the equipment via Telnet, SSH, Web, etc., which allows the administrator to configure and control network devices remotely without needing to know the IP address. This convenience is highly beneficial for network administrators when monitoring the networks they are responsible for, considering the large number of network devices and the difficulties that arise when working with documentation for remote access to equipment.

The monitoring system also has the capability to receive interrupts (trap reception functions). SNMP traps are an essential part of SNMP, enabling network devices to report potential problems. These traps are usually logged and monitored by the network administrator to track network outages and events.

When selecting specific tools for network monitoring, the administrator should first decide whether they prefer to use a proven system that has been in use for many years, or a new one. If the existing systems are more suitable, then NetFlow is the most useful tool, as it allows the use of an IP packet analyzer for the convenience of users.

The issue of ensuring the necessary quality of service (QoS) is one of the primary limiting factors in the process of transmitting multimedia messages over an IP network, and remains a subject of active research to this day. One of the promising methods for ensuring QoS in multimedia transmission over an IP network is traffic prioritization, which involves classifying network traffic into categories with different priority levels of service. To achieve this, methods for managing network resources and traffic need to be developed and studied, ensuring various levels of service quality for different real-time applications.

Network monitoring and analysis are crucial for system administrators in their daily work. Administrators must strive to keep their networks in order to avoid fragmenting performance within the company and to ensure connectivity to any existing public services. Based on the above, a range of router-oriented technologies is suitable for assisting network administrators in their daily monitoring and analysis of their networks.

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